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Student's Difficulties In Writing An Essay Descriptive

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Abstrak

This research aims to see, review, or find the difficulties of students while working on descriptive essays. The method used is a mixed method with indirect and direct interview methods summarized in the Google form. This research prepared as many as 5 questions related to obstacles and difficulties in working on descriptive essays so that students can provide their statements or answers about it. The number of students who participated in this study was 30 students. The results of the statements submitted by students are very diverse and also almost have similar factors about finding difficulties while working on descriptive essays.

Keywords: Students, Writing, Essays

BACKGROUND

Writing is an activity or a place for us to pour ideas or thoughts. There are so many benefits of writing that we can get, such as fostering creativity, strengthening memory, improving language skills, where we express our emotions or expressions and even writing can be used as an option as a hobby that can entertain ourselves. In writing, we can also make money.

In writing, there are many types of writing, such as letters, fables, poems, autobiographies, and scientific papers. In that case, this article is aimed at writing a type of writing from scientific work, namely essays. Essays become one part of scientific work because in them we provide accurate reports or data to describe, convey, and notify events or something that happens or exists among many people. Essays are also divided into several parts such as narrative essays, argumentative essays, descriptive essays, cause-and-effect essays, persuasive essays, expository essays, and analysis essays. However, this article will focus on descriptive essays.

As reported in several articles a descriptive essay is sort of what it says on the tin. It's a type of essay that describes a person or object, though it can extend to any noun, like a place, event, experience, or emotion. If you think that seems pretty broad, you're right. You're technically describing something in every essay by Alvin Park. descriptive essay is a type of composition or paper that describes an object, person, process, or event. The writer's goal is to create a vivid reading experience or to show instead of tell (metaphorically). Descriptive writing usually appeals to the five senses: taste, touch, smell, hearing, and sight. (Ex: Jack's coffee mug exploded into tiny shards of glass, catching the attention of everyone at the office.) By Jhon s.

So it can be stated that a descriptive essay is an essay that explains, expresses, displays, or describes a person, object, or place in detail so that readers can imagine what the described looks like.

In writing an essay we also need and must follow several steps. the first step in writing is pre-writing, pre-writing is where we push our minds to find or collect about the topics we want to discuss. while in the pre-writing step we also need to do brainstorming, brainstorming

is our way of getting an idea by collecting insights, ideas spontaneously or not, then the next step is developing an outline, the third step is drafting then the fourth step is revising and the last step is editing and proofreading.

The ways in writing descriptive essays are The first paragraph in your descriptive essay is the introduction. This paragraph should have four or five powerful sentences that introduce the topic you are describing to your readers. The first sentence of your introductory paragraph is your chance to grab your readers' attention. One way to do this is to make a general statement about your topic. For example, if your topic is your favorite season of the year, you might say: "Every summer I come down with a strange illness called "outside-itis." This sentence will be your topic sentence. It grabs your reader's attention and lets them know that the paragraph is going to be about spring. The topic sentence is the first sentence in your introductory paragraph.

The thesis statement follows the topic sentence in the introductory paragraph. Remember that topic or grabber sentences catch the reader's eye and tell what the paragraph is about. A thesis sentence goes a bit further. A thesis sentence states what you want your readers to know, believe, or understand after reading your essay. The thesis sentence could be in our essay about your favorite season of the year. "Each of my senses is filled up with the sights, sounds, smells, tastes, and feelings of summer." The sentence following the thesis sentence should give more information about it, and the fourth and fifth sentences should summarize your thoughts and transition to the next paragraph. The second, third, and fourth paragraphs of a descriptive essay are the body of your writing. Each paragraph in our season's essay could describe how spring affects one or more of your five senses.

The last paragraph of a descriptive essay is the conclusion. In it, you should restate the thesis sentence of your first paragraph, "Each of my senses is filled up with the sights, sounds, smells, tastes, and feelings of summer," and then summarize all the reasons you have presented for loving summer.

However, writing a descriptive essay is not as easy as we follow the rules or writing procedures in the descriptive essay itself, there are many difficulties and obstacles that we can find when we work on the descriptive essay. Starting from the difficulty of explaining how to feel about a place or person who wants to be poured into writing, then it is difficult to arrange between paragraphs so that it does not look messy, and also stick to the rules that it is a descriptive essay.

To get accurate data the author uses theory language acquisition theory Language Acquisition Theory suggests that students' proficiency in language affects their writing abilities. Students who are still developing their vocabulary, sentence structure, and grammatical skills may face challenges in accurately describing sensory details or choosing appropriate words to convey their ideas. Limited language proficiency can hinder their ability to effectively engage the reader and create a vivid picture with descriptive language oleh noam chomsky.

METHODOLOGY

This study used qualitative method. Students' descriptive essays written in English were analyzed to find difficulties in writing descriptive essays and determine the dominant difficulties. The quantitative method was only used to determine the percentage of problem aspects experienced by students in writing descriptive essays. Difficulties become the dominant obstacle to writing descriptive essays. The population of this study was 30 fourth semester students (PBI 1,2,3, and 4 classes) of the English education study program, 2021/2022 academic year. However, only students from Pbi 4 class dominate this data collection. From the students who have participated as samples for this study, it is found that they often find difficulties in describing an object and adjusting the sentence structure.

This article covers several students majoring in English, and this article is very related to the existence of courses in the English department, namely advanced writing, in which it also discusses descriptive essays. A total of 30 students majoring in English participated in participating to provide their statements contained in the questionnaire.

The technique of collecting data

In collecting data, this study used an interview instrument. This interview was conducted to find out the extent of students' understanding of descriptive essays and what difficulties they found during the descriptive essay process.

Data analysis technique

There are several categories that are reviewed in this study, namely the category of difficulty in grammar, and difficulty in choosing the right words. For the category of difficulty in composing grammar, several people who have been interviewed said that this one is a difficulty that they often encounter, some said "when writing this descriptive essay it is very difficult to determine the grammar because I myself do not necessarily master the grammar so it is still difficult and difficult to work on the essay without the help of grammar correcting tools and work on time.

Difficulty in choosing the right words and easy read, this one difficulty is also included in the category reviewed there are several interviewees who have been interviewed and said "That's right, it's very difficult for me to find the right words and easy in writing this essay, this all happens because of the lack of vocabulary that I have. The vocabulary that I have is just that, so I have difficulty in pouring the sentences that I want to convey in my essay. Then some sources also said that it was very difficult for me to pour the right words because of the lack of reading, yes reading because from reading we can find ideas and good writing but because of my lack of reading so I was less good at pouring these things.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In writing descriptive essays, it turns out that there are difficulties that students get when working on the essay, and can be seen from the answers to the questions that have been prepared. Of the 5 questions that have been prepared, not a few have almost the same answers, so they are grouped into several categories

The first is a difficulty based on structure, the second is based on the selection of grammar, and the third is based on describing in detail objects, people, and places.

Of the 30 students who answered the question, in category 1, namely difficulties based on structure, 28 people answered that they had difficulty when working on descriptive essays because of the writing structure.

In the second category, out of 30 students, 29 students stated that it was still difficult to choose or determine the appropriate language style so that readers could accept or describe what they were describing in their descriptive essays.

And the third category is that almost all of the students are still concerned about how to describe the details of the object to be written due to the lack of further observation of the object to be described in writing.

Each essay has its structure. The general structure that we usually encounter in discussing essay writing is the introduction, discussion, or content and finally the closing or commonly referred to as the conclusion. If you look at the structure of the essay, it can be categorized as easy but sometimes the easy ones often have many obstacles. Descriptive essays also have a structure that is not much different from essays in general. What distinguishes this descriptive essay is that the topic raised is more about describing or describing an object in written form. Although there are only three structures that must be gone through to produce a descriptive essay, there are still many who find it difficult in the writing process. All of these have various factors, starting from it is still difficult to express

the general idea of an object that will be described in the introduction so there are several essays whose introduction is too detailed and almost discusses the structure of the discussion or content. Then, the lack of mastering the object is described so in the discussion structure section, many students do not explain in detail about the object being observed. And finally, not fully ending a conclusion in the Essay so that if read more carefully the closing or conclusion section is sometimes still interpreted as part of the discussion or content. Even in working on an essay, many students have not been able to distinguish what a descriptive essay is and other essays. and students do not master the structure of the descriptive essay so that which makes them difficult in terms of work.

"Language style reflects the quality of the writer's writing". Of course, we have heard or seen these words. In writing an essay, language style becomes the main milestone of an essay. The more unique the language style used by the writer, the more interesting the reader will be, especially for descriptive essays. In this descriptive essay, we are required to be able to describe an object with a language style that can be felt, imagined, and able to describe the author's imagination without changing the rules of language and the object that is described and that has been determined. This is often an obstacle for writers to pour what is in the author's image to the reader. This is also one of the difficulties faced by students when working on descriptive essays, namely with several factors such as lack of mastering grammar or grammar and then not being good at choosing words and having limitations or having little vocabulary so that it is difficult to pour or make the object described into an essay.

As well as the difficulties experienced by students while working on descriptive essays is the lack of mastering the place, item, or object they describe in the essay, when being interviewed it turns out that not a few of the students who answered lacked in mastering the things they wanted to describe. They have difficulty in describing or describing because of a lack of deep understanding of the subject they want to describe, including difficulties in organizing ideas.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of this study, it can be concluded that the selection of language styles connecting sentence structures and describing objects in detail are the biggest problems that are most difficult for students during the process of writing Descriptive essays. The findings show that almost the majority of respondents have the same difficulty.

In addition, based on data collection obtained from the results of interviews, the majority of respondents said that they faced several dominating difficulties. 28 out of 30 respondents had difficulties in terms of unifying the sentence structure. Because of the lack and limitations of the sentences they have. In addition, 29 respondents also answered that they felt confused to determine the language style so that the writing was interesting to read. In addition, all respondents (30 students) who answered also found it very difficult to describe objects in detail. Because of a lack of accuracy in terms of describing something. Often they also feel hesitant in writing English essays because they think their writing is not good enough to be read.

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